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Research Article

ANALYSIS OF LEVEL OF MICRO NUTRIENTS OF HEPATITIS PATIENTS IN PAKISTAN

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Introduction: Liver is a pivotal organ of the body and play very important role in the metabolism. If there is any problem in the liver then the herbs or different plants play an important role for the treatment of liver disorders.

Objective of the study: The basic aim of the study is to find the level of micronutrients in hepatitis patients among local population of Pakistan.

Methodology of the study: This study was conducted at Nishtar Hospital, Multan during 2018. The study was conducted according to the rules and regulations of concerned committee. The data were collected from 100 patients of both genders. Detailed history was taken from all patients with special reference to duration of hepatitis, mode of infection, previous history of jaundice, HBV or HCV infection. A thorough clinical examination was carried out and stigmata of chronic liver disease, hepatosplenomegaly, ascites, etc. if present were noted.

Results: The demographic values of patient group and control group shows a significant difference. The data suggest clearly that CD4 count decreases in abnormal liver function. The results shown the table 02 demonstrates the multiple comparison of micronutrients level among patients and normal group. There were non-significant relationship present in diseased group treated with different therapies like interferon and glutathione as as $p < 0.05$. The level of micronutrients become decreases in diseased group.

Conclusion: It is concluded that hepatitis directly increase the liver enzymes even after receiving medication and other therapies.

Key words: Hepatitis, Patients, Therapy, Enzymes.

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INTRODUCTION:

Liver is a pivotal organ of the body and play very important role in the metabolism. If there is any problem in the liver, then the herbs or different plants play an important role for the treatment of liver disorders [1]. There are a number of plants which shows hepatoprotective property. Hepatitis B and C viruses can lead to hepatocellular carcinoma and cirrhosis-related end-stage liver disease, which are potentially life-threatening liver diseases. Hepatitis B and C need immediate worldwide attention as the infection rates are too high. More than 240 million people globally have chronic (long-term) liver infections. Every year, about 600,000 people die because of the acute or chronic consequences of hepatitis B, and more than 350,000 people die from hepatitis C-related liver diseases worldwide [2].

Hepatitis is a major public health problem and is endemic throughout the world especially in tropical and developing countries. Hepatitis means inflammation of the liver. The liver is indispensable to our survival [3]. It has synthetic, storage and detoxification functions. An abnormal LFT may signify a serious disease that can be identified only through further testing. These conditions include liver diseases, such as primary biliary cirrhosis (PBC), diseases of other organs such as Paget's disease of bone, and multi-organ diseases such as haemochromatosis. However, the majority of people with an abnormal LFT in primary care settings will not have any such previously undetected disease [4]. They will have either no disease at all, or will be manifesting the effects of alcohol abuse or obesity. The doctor is likely to be aware, or at least suspicious, of these behaviours when ordering LFTs, but this does not exclude the presence of other diseases that may aggravate liver damage. There is thus a real question about which specific further tests, if any, a GP should order when an abnormal LFT result is obtained in a patient with non-specific symptoms, or as a result of routine testing [5].

Objective of the study

The basic aim of the study is to find the level of micronutrients in hepatitis patients among local population of Pakistan.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This study was conducted at Nishtar Hospital, Multan during 2018. The study was conducted according to the rules and regulations of concerned committee. The data were collected from 100 patients of both genders. Detailed history was taken from all patients with special reference to duration of hepatitis, mode of infection, previous history of jaundice, HBV or HCV infection. A thorough clinical examination was carried out and stigmata of chronic liver disease, hepatosplenomegaly, ascites, etc. if present were noted.

Blood analysis

It includes Hemoglobin (Hb), total leucocytes count (TLC), differential leucocytes count (DLC), platelet count, level of micronutrients and LFT were done in all patients. The LFT included serum bilirubin, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), serum alkaline phosphatase (SAP) and serum albumin. Abnormal values were defined as serum Bilirubin ≥ 1.5 mg/dl, ALT/AST ≥ 50 IU/ml.

Statistical analysis

The data were sampled and entered into the SPSS worksheet for analysis. The alpha criterion was set at 0.05. After constructing a 2x2 contingency table, chi-square without Yates correction was used to find the association between the potential risk factors and hepatitis status.

RESULTS:

The demographic values of patient group and control group shows a significant difference. The data suggest clearly that CD4 count decreases in abnormal liver function. The results shown the table 02 demonstrates the multiple comparison of micronutrients level among patients and normal group. There were non-significant relationship present in diseased group treated with different therapies like interferon and glutathione as as $p < 0.05$. The level of micronutrients become decreases in diseased group.

Table 01: Associations of Clinical Parameters with Abnormal Liver Function Tests

Parameter	Normal LFTs	Abnormal LFTs	P value
Age (years)	35.3 + 6.7	36.5 + 10.1	0.54
Sex (M:F)	237:35 (87.1%:12.5%)	45:3 (93.8%:6.2%)	0.91
BMI (kg/m ²)	21.8 ± 1.8	21.7 ± 2.7	0.88
Duration of HIV infection (months)	36 ± 50.3	38 ± 43.8	0.95
CD4 count (/mm ³)	280 ± 182	234 ± 212	0.12
Significant alcohol consumption	106 (38.9%)	24 (50%)	0.15
HBV & HCV Co-infection	47 (17.2%)	19 (39.6%)	0.002
HBsAg positive	26 (9.6%)	11 (22.9%)	0.01
Anti HCV positive	21 (7.7%)	06 (12.5%)	0.27

Table 02: Analysis of micronutrients in control group and diseased group

	F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Std. Error Difference
Zinc	1.668	.208	3.798	25	.001	31.206435
			3.531	15.155	.003	33.564560
Iron	24.927	.000	4.189	25	.000	.321750
			3.336	10.037	.008	.404044
Silinium	1.592	.219	17.193	25	.000	.340691
			16.431	16.498	.000	.356485

DISCUSSION:

Damage to the structural integrity of liver is reflected by an increase in the level of serum transaminase because these are cytoplasmic in location and are released into circulation after cellular damage [8]. It is generally accepted that the toxicity of carbon tetrachloride depends on the cleavage of the carbon-chlorine bond to generate a trichloromethyl free radical, and this free radical reacts rapidly with oxygen to form a trichloro methyl peroxy radical, which may contribute to the hepatotoxicity and subsequent increase in hepatic enzymes [9].

Essential micronutrients are involved in many metabolic pathways in the liver, such as enzymatic functions and protein synthesis, oxidative damage and anti-oxidant defense, immunological competence, interferon therapy response regulations, and alterations of the virus genomes. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) have also been implicated in a number of hepatic pathologies in exacerbating liver diseases [10]. The oxidant production associated with immune reactions against viral hepatitis leads to the formation of hepatocellular carcinoma. Therefore, the changes in micronutrients and their demolishing effects against oxidative stress are factors for viral hepatitis pathogenesis [8].

HCV is a major cause of chronic liver disease. HCV infection frequently leads to chronic hepatitis with increasing risk of developing liver cirrhosis and HCC. Interferon with or without ribavirin is the only drug with proven efficacy in treating chronic HCV infections. Unfortunately, these therapeutic models maintain the rate of sustained virologic response (SVR) to approximately 10-40% [12].

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that hepatitis directly increases the liver enzymes even after receiving medication and other therapies. The distribution of micronutrients activities in blood may be an additional host-specific parameter with a predictive value for the responsiveness of patients to interferon therapy.

REFERENCES:

1. Jain P, Prakash S, Gupta S, Singh KP, Shrivastava S, Singh DD, Singh J, Jain A. Prevalence of hepatitis A virus, hepatitis B virus, hepatitis C virus, hepatitis D virus and hepatitis E virus as causes of acute viral hepatitis in North India: a hospital-based study. *Indian J Med Microbio*. 2013;31(3):261-5.
2. Pradhan SC and C Girish (2006). Hepato protective herbal drug, silymarin from

- experimental pharmacology to clinical medicine
Indian J Med Res 124, pp 491-504.
3. Patel, V.K. and Bhatt H.V., 1985. Toxicity antiseptic effect of chicory root extract in Pyorrhoea. The antiseptic 904-906.
 4. Chen C.-H., Yang P.-M., Huang G.-T., Lee H.-S., Sung J.-L., Sheu J.-C. Estimation of seroprevalence of hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus in Taiwan from a large-scale survey of free hepatitis screening participants. *Journal of the Formosan Medical Association*. 2007;106(2):148-155. doi: 10.1016/S0929-6646(09)60231-X.
 5. Ward J. W. The hidden epidemic of hepatitis C virus infection in the United States: occult transmission and burden of disease. *Topics in Antiviral Medicine*. 2013;21(1):15-19.
 6. Seeff L. B. Natural history of chronic hepatitis C. *Hepatology*. 2002;36(5, supplement 1):S35-S46. doi: 10.1053/jhep.2002.36806.
 7. Li X., Jeffers L. J., Garon C., et al. Persistence of hepatitis C virus in a human megakaryoblastic leukaemia cell line. *Journal of Viral Hepatitis*. 1999;6(2):107-114. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2893.1999.00140.x
 8. *Blood Screening by Blood Center*. Taiwan Blood Services Foundation; 2009. <http://www.sc.blood.org.tw/Internet/main/docDetail.aspx?uid=6677&pid=6389&docid=24905>.
 9. Crapnell K., Zanjani E. D., Chaudhuri A., Ascensao J. L., Jeor S. S., Maciejewski J. P. In vitro infection of megakaryocytes and their precursors by human cytomegalovirus. *Blood*. 2000;95(2):487-493.
 10. Gavrillovskaia I. N., Shepley M., Shaw R., Ginsberg M. H., Mackow E. R. β_3 integrins mediate the cellular entry of hantaviruses that cause respiratory failure. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*. 1998;95(12):7074-7079. doi: 10.1073/pnas.95.12.7074.
 11. Martell M., Gomez J., Esteban J. I., et al. High-throughput real-time reverse transcription-PCR quantitation of hepatitis C virus RNA. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology*. 1999;37(2):327-332.
 12. Amin J., Kaye M., Skidmore S., Pillay D., Cooper D.A., Dore G.J. HIV and hepatitis C coinfection within the CAESAR study. *HIV Med*. 2004;5:174-179.